

The selected proposals of support to cancer patients – coaching and physiotherapy

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Abstract

The present paper addresses the subject of applying physiotherapy and coaching in the treatment of cancer patients. Currently, more than 12.5 million cancers are diagnosed in the world every year, with annual mortality of 7.6 million people. The situation of patients is fraught with challenges and hence requires significant strength and determination. What seems to be of particular importance is to ensure adequate support not only for therapy of cancer patients themselves but also for their family members and the medical personnel taking care of them. Health coaching may be a means of support for all of these groups. Physiotherapy, when introduced before, in the course of or after completion of the treatment, may potentially promise some benefits for the patients. Nowadays, there is no doubt that rehabilitation is a safe and effective form of supporting cancer care and restoring the patient's psychophysical well-being, and it is the avoidance of physical activity that can intensify the symptoms of side effects. However, it is still often ignored. It is worth pointing out that a multidisciplinary approach to patients is the most effective solution, especially in chronic diseases. Patients can receive support and advice from different side of medical care. This provides opportunities to adapt the treatment to the individual needs of a given person. It is also important to involve family members and informal caregiver in the treatment and active and effective care process. The health care system may facilitate positive results by treating caregivers as partners in the health care team as well as providing them with instructions and guidelines on how to pursue this role.

Keywords: coaching, cancer, support, physiotherapy

Introduction

Central and Eastern Europe, and thus also Poland, is at significant risk of deaths primarily caused by cancers. Currently, more than 12.5 million cancers are diagnosed in the world every year, with mortality of 7.6 million people per year. Epidemiological forecasts indicate that these numbers are likely to double in the next 15-20 years (in 2030, cancer prevalence is estimated at 26.5 million patients, with mortality of 17.1 million). The number of new cancer cases in Poland is 160 thousand per year, resulting in more than 90 thousand deaths. A comprehensive method of fighting cancer encompasses the following aspects: epidemiology and cancer registry; planning and controlling research; teaching, health education and organisation of constant social fight against neoplastic diseases; prevention, detection, diagnosis and treatment of cancer patients; psychophysical rehabilitation and terminal care; maintaining continuous documentation and permanent care of cancer patients until the end of their life as well as socioeconomic assessment of the results of all the activities within oncology[1]. Research and clinical practice are closely linked in the area of fighting neoplasms, and the ultimate objective of this activity is to reduce prevalence and increase the number of cured patients, and hence to decrease cancer mortality. These assumptions and objectives can certainly not be

fulfilled without adequate involvement of psychophysical rehabilitation. The human body and its physical aspects together with the broadly conceived psycho-spiritual dimensions form an inseparable whole, which constantly undergoes complicated and interlinked life processes [1].

The role of physiotherapy in oncological treatment

Physiotherapy is now commonly used in almost every field of medicine. Unfortunately, in the case of oncology, a problem arises when the patient treats the disease as a death sentence. The issues of paramount importance in this regard concern the moment of the diagnosis and the physician's skilful guidance offers to the patient. Rehabilitation, when introduced before, in the course of or after the treatment, may be extremely beneficial for patients. However, it is still often ignored. The universality of physiotherapy in oncology means that it should be equally available to each cancer patient, irrespective of the type, severity or selected method of treatment. Particular stress should be laid on physiotherapy administered prior to cancer treatment, which contributes to reducing the risk of complications and disorders, while increasing the chances of faster recovery.

Diagram 1. The benefits of physical activity in cancer patients Source: own work on the basis of [3]

It should also be noted that cancer patients should often receive rehabilitation from the moment of diagnosis, though their hospitalisation, until the end of their life. It is recommended that rehabilitation encompass all aspects of the patient’s life – medical, psychosocial and professional. This should minimise the relapse of functional disorders which are still dangerous years after completion of therapy [2]. Physical activity, however, has many advantages for cancer patients (Diagram 1).

Until quite recently, any kind of physical activity by cancer patients would raise concerns and suspicions. It was believed that it would further weaken the patient’s immunity, exacerbate the treatment side effects or increase the risk of injuries. It is obvious, however, that the patient’s poor psychophysical well-being and negative attitude to exercising were also the factors that spoke in favour of “leave the patient unbothered”. The feeling of fatigue is one of the main symptoms in those patients, with approximately 30% of them still experiencing it after 3 years of their treatment [4]. However, in fact, quite the opposite is true. Nowadays, there is no longer any doubt that physiotherapy is a safe and effective form of supporting cancer care and restoring the patient’s psychophysical well-being, and it is the avoidance of physical activity that can intensify the symptoms of side effects.

Each patient should be treated individually and physiotherapy should be adapted to their possibilities (Table 1).

The Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group’s Performance Status Rating (ECOG-PSR) is a widely used single-item rating scale based on a patient’s ability to perform usual activities without needing to rest. It is also worth considering the patient’s preferences so that rehabilitation is treated not only as an improvement process, but also as a source of pleasure, happiness and satisfaction. Cancer patients can and should practice all types of physical exercises, adapted to their personal needs, at all stages of the disease and during different forms of treatment. For this reason, a good solution is to consult a physiotherapist in order to prepare such a rehabilitation programme that would satisfy the patient’s requirements, while being the most effective and safe. Rehabilitation should be administered after surgeries or during radio- and chemotherapy as a form of treatment rather than prophylaxis. Physical activity not only improves psychophysical well-being by facilitating and accelerating full recovery, but also increases the body’s immunity and mental condition, so important in cancer treatment. Studies indicate that physically fit and active patients have a significantly lower (even by 50%) risk of cancer occurrence or recurrence and of premature death [6,7].

Table 1. The Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group’s Performance Status Rating (ECOG-PSR) [5]

Level	Functional status
0	Fully functional status
1	Restricted In terms of physically strenuous activity but ambulatory and able to perform light work
2	Ambulatory and capable of all self-care but unable to carry out any work. Out of a bed more than 50% of walking hours.
3	Capable of only limited self-care, confined to a bed or chair for more than 50% of walking hours
4	Completely disabled
5	Dead

There is overwhelming evidence that training sessions undertaken during chemotherapy can contribute to the maintenance of cardiopulmonary fitness and muscular strength, while reducing fatigue, mood disorders and lean body mass [8] and enhancing self-reported functioning [9], overall HRQoL [8,9] and the functions of the immune system [10]. The main goals of physiotherapy in oncology are presented in Table 2 (Table 2).

Many healthcare providers find it difficult to recognise cancer as a chronic disease, which poses a limitation and prevents them from issuing referrals for physiotherapy. The long-term side effects of cancer treatment are either unidentified or accepted by the patients as “the price which has to be paid”. In some cases, physiotherapy is regarded as too time-consuming for patients with restricted life expectancy. They take no notice of the fact that simple treatments like learning how to move from the bed onto a chair, changing position or assuming an upright posture may considerably enhance the comfort and autonomy even in the final stages of life. On the other hand, patients after treatment are often under pressure and have low expectations of their health, especially if they are not familiar with the possibilities of solving functional problems [11].

What is health coaching?

In the contemporary world, almost everyone knows the concept of coaching. It is often associated with personal development, professional career and the work towards achieving the so-called life-work balance [12]. In a word, it is about improving the quality of life. When we find ourselves at the crossroads and are unsure which path to follow, we often seek support of a coach to help us achieve our goals. The questions the coach asks, which are based on the resources we already have, help us achieve what we desired. If coaching produces such excellent results, why isn't it so commonly used in the clinic practice? It seems that it is only the matter of time required to conduct numerous studies to verify the usefulness of coaching in the context of various health-related areas. There are numerous examples in the literature showing the application of this process in medicine and health sciences. It is defined as a form of support for patients, their families and caregivers. The effectiveness of coaching is verified by carrying out randomised controlled trials. There are also descriptions in the form of a case study. Increasing numbers of prestigious universities today are offering coaching courses. The demand for such services might be evidenced, for example, by the number of schools that offer courses for future coaches. Is it a universal remedy that cures all illnesses? Surely not, but if this is something that might even slightly help patients in

the struggle to improve their well-being, it is worth a closer examination [12,13,14,15,16,17,18].

The situation that the patients, their families and caregivers need to face may generate various difficulties, for instance related to an increased number of duties, the fulfilment of all the medical recommendations or a change in the diet. A disease often forces patients to modify their lifestyle. Coaching is a helpful process especially in the context of changes and searching for new possibilities or optimum solutions. Taking into account the fact that the literature features numerous definitions of this process, the one presented below is – in the authors' opinions – the most accurate and fully reflects the meaning of this construct. Health coaching has been defined by Stephen Palmer as “the practice of health education and health promotion within a coaching context, to enhance the well-being of individuals and facilitate the achievement of their health-related goals” [13]. This field of coaching is still developing [12]. Palmer points out that “health coaching is becoming another option for clients, patients and employees who wish to change their health-related behaviours” [12]. Co-Active Life Coaching is also considered to be a promising form of support for patients coping with various health problems [14]. In the case of patients with chronic diseases, health coaching seems to be effective and its effects persist for over a year [15].

The role of coaching in oncological treatment

How can coaching be implemented into patient care? The literature gives various proposals. Coaching is sometimes part of major interventions, for example it can be used in combination with other forms of support, sometimes being the only differentiating element between various study groups. Moreover, thanks to the development of technology, it is no longer necessary to restrict coaching to face-to-face sessions. The effectiveness of telephone-based coaching, messages from e-coach or coaching based on web platforms and e-mail coaching is also being increasingly verified and assessed by researchers. It seems that time is priceless in certain contexts and, once lost, it cannot be regained. The advantage is therefore the possibility to save the time by avoiding the inconvenience of having to move from place to place (e.g. covering the distance between home and the coaching office). This possibility is offered by the use of modern technologies. There are many potential benefits of the coaching process, for instance higher self-efficacy [16,17], increased involvement in the treatment process [16], taking more informed decisions [17], better assessment of quality of life [18], improved stress management [17] as well as more active development of one's health-conscious habits and the future [12,13,16]. Selected benefits are presented in the figure below (Figure 1).

Table.2The goals of physiotherapy in oncology

The goals of physiotherapy in oncology
psychological and physical preparation of the patients for the scheduled cancer treatment
prevention of complications and functional disorders related to the cancer treatment
support for the process of returning to psychophysical well-being and gaining maximum autonomy and independence
decreasing the risk of relapse and premature death

Figure 1. The benefits of coaching in chronic diseases. Source: own work on the basis of [16]

Figure 2. The goals of coaching in chronic diseases. Source: own work on the basis of [16]

Health coaching has objectives that are also shared by numerous scientific disciplines, particularly in the field of health sciences and medicine. The figure below (Figure 2) presents selected objectives of coaching in the context of patients suffering from chronic diseases.

In the case of cancer patients, coaching in combination with education may translate into “improvement in average pain levels” [19]. Taking into consideration all the possible benefits, it is worth taking a scientific look at further verification of using coaching as support for cancer patients.

Coaching in physiotherapy

It stands to reason to combine the power of coaching and physiotherapy. Moreover, a coach may support the patient in preparing a realistic action plan, laying out goals that the patient would like to pursue. It seems that the assistance offered to the patient should be multifaceted, meaning that we should pay attention to the physical and mental aspects alike. How much easier it would be for us to achieve our goals and stay committed to our resolutions despite a variety of obstacles if we felt that our actions are meaningful and knew not just the first step on our way but the subsequent stages as well.

Mallows and Francis-Wright argue that peer coaching, in the opinion of physiotherapy students, is regarded as a useful method of developing clinical reasoning skills [20]. The results of the studies on the usefulness of telephone-based coaching as support for patients with knee osteoarthritis indicate that there is no differentiation in the results [21]. It was demonstrated that coaching can help lung cancer patients in increasing the amount of information on pain, which they present to their providers during routine appointments [22]. An overview of studies on the effectiveness of telephone-based coaching for sufferers of chronic diseases suggests that this method could bring positive results [23].

However, there are studies which demonstrate that the participation of physicians in coaching sessions may translate into their increased resilience and higher self-awareness [17]. Furthermore, the authors of the studies suggest that the benefits of coaching for a physician may also have a positive impact on patient care [17].

The combination of knowledge from these two disciplines, namely physiotherapy and coaching psychology seems to be a promising solution. However, in order to verify this thesis, it is necessary to conduct further studies.

As has already been mentioned, a disease does not only concern one person. Therefore, the subsequent points

stress the importance of support for the patient’s family and the medical personnel.

Support for the patient's family

Nowadays, there are practically no families who have not been affected by a chronic disease. Such a disease completely changes the functioning of patients themselves, but also of their close family and relatives. This is the case with cancer. A neoplastic disease never concerned the patient alone. It is also the family members and friends who are engaged in the treatment and experience concerns and strong emotions. In the language of psychology, they are referred to as “secondary patients”. The relatives and family members of cancer patients also need various forms of support. They typically look for emotional and information support. It is essential for them to give vent to strong and natural emotions, such as fear, sadness, sorrow, anger and wrath. The patient’s relatives and family members request emotional support in order to be able to deal with the stressful situation of the disease in a composed and effective manner, thereby wishing to provide support to the patient. This will never be possible if they show nervousness, aggression and fear themselves. Another form of support is searching the information needed by the patient. The most important issues in this regard include the methods of treatment, recognised specialists in different areas of medicine and recommended health care facilities. It is also common for caregivers of cancer patients to search for answers to their own important questions [24]. Studies indicated that partners and other family members experience similar, and sometimes even higher levels of stress than cancer patients, with anxiety and depression being two of the most common problems reported. Other emotions may also occur, including the feeling of fear, uncertainty, hopelessness, reluctance and mood changes [25]. Furthermore, the individuals who take care of patients have their own emotional reactions to the diagnosis and prognosis of the patients, and hence may require training or emotional support (coaching) themselves. The health care system may facilitate positive results by treating caregivers as partners in the health care team as well as providing them with instructions and guidelines on how to pursue this role.

Support for the medical personnel working with cancer patients

It is also worth considering what we can offer to medical personnel who have to cope with a number of difficult emotions or events on a daily basis. It is not uncommon for patients or their families to get lost in the new situation, to feel anger, fear or a mixture of emotions

which might cause them to go beyond the standards of good behaviour. The individuals that calm them down and answer their countless questions are the nurses, physiotherapists and physicians. It seems that this group is already offered many training courses, for example in good patient communication or techniques for dealing with aggressive behaviour. It would also be worth considering more frequent implementation of coaching. Encouragingly, this is an action that has already been implemented in a number of countries. Why? Because it appears that coaching may be useful also for the medical personnel, thereby potentially improving physician quality of life [18].

Summary

Taking into account the issues related to neoplastic disease and the difficulties encountered at the moment of diagnosis, during the treatment or recovery, it is a subject of great importance. This is also true due to the fact that, according to the available statistics, this disease is becoming increasingly widespread in the world. Taking these arguments into account, it is necessary to search for methods that would make it possible to cope with the whole situation as effectively as possible. At this point, it is important to stress both the physical and the psychological aspects of the patient, as well as look at the patient's situation from different perspectives. After all, it is not only the patient who needs to fight with the disease. This obligation also passes onto the patient's next of kin. A cancer diagnosis puts all the family members at the test in a sudden and violent way. This is the moment when they have to remember that they become the so-called "secondary patients" and will be likely to require support too. It is also worth mentioning the medical personnel who are working in the specific environment of an oncological ward. They are often extremely vulnerable to professional burnout. In this case, it is also recommended to implement, besides physiotherapy, coaching sessions, which would help maintain balance and support not only the patients but also the individuals around them.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.